

**CURRENT IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW PRINCIPLES IN PROVIDING
COMMUNICATION BETWEEN GOVERNMENT OFFICES AND THE
PEOPLE**

Kasimova Zumrad

Teacher of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7187610>

In the context of the development of a democratic legal state and civil society in our country, ensuring the priority of the rights and interests of citizens is defined as the priority direction of our state policy. After all, the provision of human rights, needs and interests is the guarantee of democratic reforms implemented in our country. It is not for nothing that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev did not focus on such vital and profound calls as "The people should serve the people, not the state agencies, but the state agencies should serve our people", "People should be satisfied with us" and the principles that are the program for our activities. Any management is evaluated by its effective result and viability. In particular, at the initiative of the President, 2017 was declared the "Year of Communication with the People and Human Interests". The vivid practical expression of this initiative was expressed in the Action Strategy for the Development of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021.

During the years of independence, effective legal frameworks for ensuring the rights and interests of citizens were created in our country and are constantly being improved. In this regard, the role, status and activity mechanism of state management bodies and public organizations were formed. But in today's era of globalization, it requires systematic updates and modernization in all spheres of state and social life. In this regard, a number of reforms are being implemented in our country during the current year and are continuing consistently.

The main issue on today's agenda is communication with the people, appeals, and ensuring the interests of citizens. In particular, the effectiveness of the state and economic management bodies in this regard is being critically discussed. Appeals of citizens mainly arise in matters related to the activities of competent state and economic management bodies. Citizens' appeals to state and economic management bodies mainly arise in general directions such as protecting the rights and interests of citizens, solving problems in real situations, providing methodological and practical assistance in this regard, and coordinating the activities of state and non-state public associations. It is possible to recognize the cooperation of the state bodies with the directly competent state bodies and non-state organizations in the main mechanisms of solving citizens' appeals.

Today, state bodies serve the people and consider appeals within the legally established powers of the management system organizations. In cooperation with non-governmental organizations, the principles of public control and social partnership are relied upon.

In general, the service and effective functioning of government agencies for the people requires a number of democratic reforms and measures. In particular, the establishment of state bodies on a democratic basis. In this regard, our country has accumulated a lot of experience, and during the years of independence, the system of populist state power was gradually developed. Today, as a result of the President's initiative and practical policy, changes are taking place in this area as well. For example, the activities of deputies and senators elected by the people in the legislative power system were critically analyzed. It was emphasized that the basis of his activity is communication with the people. Appropriate measures have been taken in this regard.

To what extent does the development and adoption of the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Control" increase the effectiveness of the performance of the tasks assigned to state bodies, their observance of human rights, freedoms and interests, and the response of the heads of state bodies to the on-the-spot resolution of citizens' appeals and problems raised by them allows to establish public control over reporting.

Today, the implementation of measures aimed at the establishment of "People's Reception Rooms" in each district (city) for considering the appeals of individuals and legal entities, considering proposals, applications and complaints of individuals and legal entities, constant and open communication with the population, their provides a detailed study and solution of their problems, as well as an increase in the population's trust in the state. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities", which was recently adopted in a new version, has a new approach to the following issues: expansion of interactive methods of receiving and considering appeals; to publish the results of consideration of appeals; review and resolution of repeated appeals, features of mobile reception of citizens; organization of remote reception of citizens using a video conference; Determining the general rules of the "People's Reception" institution; Legal grounds for receiving and considering appeals through "Hotlines". At the same time, a separate department (department, group) for working with appeals is being established in each state and economic management body and local government bodies.

It should be noted that the current reforms in the judicial system are a guarantee of ensuring the legal rights and interests of citizens. Tasks such as further specialization of courts, strengthening of the judicial apparatus, strengthening of the social position of judges and the implementation of potential personnel policy, the introduction of systems and structures that help the administration of justice and the authority of the judiciary are being solved.

Reforms in the field of ensuring reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens are also important. In this regard, the main attention is paid to the activities of law enforcement agencies. In particular, the organization of virtual reception rooms of the heads of all law enforcement and control bodies, increasing the transparency and effectiveness of ensuring human rights and freedoms, considering the state of economic development, modern requirements, international standards, as well as the wide involvement of information and communication technologies. and development of the Concept project for 2018-2021 on the improvement of criminal procedural legislation, etc.

On the basis of the principle that "state agencies should serve our people", the tasks in the following areas were defined and new mechanisms are being formed in solving citizens' appeals:

First, further democratization and optimization of the activities of state management agencies, in particular, executive bodies. In this direction, the task of developing the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan was set, and the decree of the head of our state on September 8 of this year "On approval of the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was signed. This document is aimed at eliminating the problems and shortcomings that prevent the successful implementation of the state policy on modernization of economic sectors and social sphere, comprehensive development of regions, improvement of the standard of living and well-being of the population.

Secondly, formation of public management personnel based on the principles of meritocracy. Attracting modern thinking, initiative, responsible, professionally trained personnel to the public service. Formation and promotion of a positive social-professional image of management bodies and management personnel.

Thirdly, to introduce an efficient and modern system of eliminating bureaucratic obstacles.

Fourth, raising the legal-political consciousness and culture of citizens. This task determines the content of state and citizen relations. A citizen should develop a

sense of belonging and an active citizenship position. Only then will he deeply understand that the state office serves for the sake of the solution. Understands the reforms being implemented and has a critical-analytical outlook.

At this point, it is worth noting that the following issues should also be paid attention to in order to serve the people of the state agencies and solve citizens' appeals in a timely manner:

First of all, when solving citizens' appeals, based on the content of the appeal, they should be assigned to the competent state office and control the decision only in the system of this authorized office. Because sometimes the execution of the issue related to the authorized office is carried out by another organization and institution;

Secondly, resolving appeals and interests, communicating with the people should not turn into "reformism";

Thirdly, to pay more attention to the practical result and evaluation of appeals rather than the process of consideration and resolution;

Fourth, to strengthen the high ethical and professional training of law enforcement agencies and system employees and to show an example of active citizenship.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси. -Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2018.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида”ги 2017 йил 7 февралдаги ПФ-4947-сонли Фармони.
3. Kistaubayev, S. (2021). THE HUMAN FACTOR IN THE GLOBALIZATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(12), 1062-1066.
4. Кистаубаев, С. У. (2018). ВЗАИМНОЕ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО СЕМЬИ, МАХАЛЛЫ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННОСТИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ. Наука и мир, 2(4), 26-28.
5. Mukhammadsidiqov, M., & Turaev, A. (2020). Influence of us neoconservatism on formation of national security paradigm. The Light of Islam, 2020(3), 113-120.
6. MUHAMMADSIDIKOV, M. (2015). Özbekistan'da toplumsal yaşamın ana özelliği hoşgörü. Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, (54), 7-14.
7. Muhammadsidiqov, M. (2015). Stability of North African Region. Int. J. of Multidisciplinary and Current research, 3, 7-14.

8. Mukhammadolim, M. (2019). Problems of regulation of secularism and religious principles in Arab countries. *Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research*, (4 (6)), 114-122.
9. Mukhammadsidiqov, M. M. (2019). THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENERGY SECTOR IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THE ROLE OF UZBEKISTAN IN IT. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 532-534.
10. Mukhammadsidiqov, M., & Turaev, A. (2020). The Influence Of The Energy Factor On Modern International Relations. *The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology*, 2(12), 5-15.
11. Nazirov, M., & Mukhammadsidiqov, M. (2020). Central Asia: Involvement of Afghanistan in Regional Development Processes. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(12), 266-272.
12. Исроилова, Г., & Мухаммадсиддиқов, М. (2021). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ДИНИЙ-МАЪРИФИЙ СОҲАНИНГ ЖАМИЯТ ИЖТИМОИЙ-СИЁСИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИГИДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 196-200).
13. Turaev, A. (2021). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONSERVATIVE IDEAS IN THE UNITED STATES. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
14. Salokhiddinovich, T. A. (2022). The Ideology of Neoconservatism: Theoretical and Political-Categorical Analysis. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 296-300.
15. Salokhiddinovich, T. A. (2021). A study of the political ideology of us neoconservatism: comparison of interpretations of western and russian scholars. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 723-728.
16. Zuhridin, K., Sokhibovna, S. S., & Salokhiddinovich, T. A. (2022). Enlightenment Against Ignorance. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 359-361.
17. Amanlayev, A. X., & Toshboyev, B. E. THE ROLE OF EXAMPLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL MENTALITY. *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 288.
18. Hakimovich, A. A., & Pulatovna, E. M. (2022). THE ROLE OF ISLAMIC VALUES AND ENLIGHTENMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONAL MORAL QUALITIES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(1), 327-330.

19. Pulatovna, E. M. (2021). Women's activity is an important factor of society development. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(1), 1074-1078.
20. Pulatovna, E. M., & Mirjalol, M. (2022). The Place Of Public Opinion In The Socio-Political Life Of Society. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 6, 177-181.

